

**TIME SERIES PREDICTION OF TCI INDEX USING LSTM AND
MAPPING VEHICULAR CARBON MONOXIDE EMISSION FOR
NEW DELHI**

*A dissertation report submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for
the award of the degree of*

**INTEGRATED DUAL DEGREE B. TECH (CSE) + M. TECH WITH
SPECIALISATION IN
ARTIFITIAL INTELLIGENCE AND ROBOTICS**

SUBMITTED BY:

SAWAR GUPTA

17/ICS/084

SUPERVISED BY:

DR. VIMLESH KUMAR RAY

&

CO-SUPERVISED BY:

DR. ANUJ PRAKASH

**DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING
SCHOOL OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY
GAUTAM BUDDHA UNIVERSITY
GREATER NOIDA – 201312, UTTAR PRADESH
JUNE, 2022**

UNIVERSITY SCHOOL OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION
TECHNOLOGY, GAUTAM BUDDHA UNIVERSITY, GREATER NOIDA-201312,

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Place: Greater Noida

**School of ICT
Gautam Buddha University
Greater Noida, (U.P.)**

**SCHOOL OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY
GAUTAM BUDDHA UNIVERSITY, GREATER NOIDA, 201312**

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It is certified that the thesis entitled, "**TIME SERIES PREDICTION OF TCI INDEX USING LSTM AND MAPPING VEHICULAR CARBON MONOXIDE EMISSION FOR NEW DELHI**" has been carried out by **Sawar Gupta (17/ICS/084)** under my supervision. He has fulfilled the mandatory requirements for the submission of this research work. In my opinion, this work is fully adequate, in scope and quality, as a thesis for the degree of **Integrated B. Tech. (CSE) + M. Tech. (AIR)**. To the best of my knowledge, the results presented in this thesis have not been submitted in part or full to any other University/Institute/Organization for the award of any degree/diploma. However, responsibility for any plagiarism-related issue solely stands with the student.

Vimlesh
29/6/22

School of ICT
Gautam Buddha University
Greater Noida, (U.P.)

Dr. Vimlesh Kumar Ray

Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering,
School of Information and Communication Technology,
Gautam Buddha University, Greater Noida, (UP)

Anuj Prakash

Dr. Anuj Prakash

Leader, Analytics and Insights
Tata Consultancy Services
Bengaluru, (KA)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Throughout my dissertation, I have been very fortunate to get help and support from many people. I feel immense pleasure in expressing my profound gratitude to my supervisor during the dissertation **Dr Vimlesh Kumar Ray** (Faculty, School of ICT), and Dr. **Anuj Prakash** (Leader Analytics and Insights, Tata Consultancy Services) who's encouragement, guidance and support from the initial to the final level enabled me to develop an understanding of the subject. Their willingness to constantly motivate and guide me contributed tremendously to this dissertation work. I am also thankful to **Prof. Snajay Kumar Sharma** (Dean, School of ICT) and **Dr. Navaid Z. Rizvi** (Faculty, School of ICT) for guiding me through the course on this dissertation.

Besides, I would like to thank the authority of the University School Of Information and Communication Technology (USICT), Gautam Buddha University for providing a good environment and facilities that helped me complete this dissertation.

Lastly, I offer my regards and blessings to all of those who supported me in any respect during the completion of the research project.

Sawar Gupta

17/ICS/084

ABSTRACT

The fast growth of urban India has resulted in a massive increase in the number of automobiles on the road. This has doubled in certain cities during the last decade. In recent years, rapid urbanization and the expansion of motor vehicles, have had a significant impact on human life and the environment. The congestion on roads has increased significantly, for the city like New Delhi. But in today's fast changing world unprecedented potential for enhancing transportation and air quality management have emerged as a result of the growing usage of intelligent transportation system data, in smart-city programmers throughout the world. This has open new avenues for researchers where this available data could be utilized for various study in order to optimize traffic monitoring, prediction and forecasting, which could be further used for efficient policy formulation by governments and different societies.

This work first mentions the various different approaches for prediction being used in today's world ranging from statistical techniques to machine learning techniques, it further mentions various different approaches which were being used to map road level vehicular emissions. Then moving forward different previously published work are analyzed and a gap is identified where city specific study hasn't been conducted for New Delhi where TCI Index of the city is being predicted and this data is being utilized to prepare vehicular emission inventory of Carbon Monoxide. Finally a model is being proposed to predict TCI Index for the city using deep learning time series prediction algorithm i.e. Long Short Term Memory.

The index was further used to prepare a road level Carbon dioxide vehicular emission inventory at hourly flux for over eight weeks of time period. In order to improve the intelligence and accuracy of vehicle emission control, this study offers a unique method for creating high-resolution traffic emission inventories that may be used in many different kinds of cities, especially in those that faces a scarcity of publically available data.

The analysis of simulation result is presented in graphical form where the graph generated from the predicted values has identified the trend of actual values with high precision and the Carbon Monoxide emission inventory has also been successfully generated, and has been represented in the form of area graph in perfect timestamp order.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CO	Carbon Monoxide
NOX	Nitrogen Oxide
AI	Artificial Intelligence
PM.25	Particulate Matter
DL	Deep Learning
TCI	Traffic Control Index
LSTM	Long Short Term Memory
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
ML	Machine Learning
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
TCS	Tata Consultancy Services
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
ATIS	Advanced Traffic Information Systems
ATMS	Advanced Traffic Management Systems
PeMS	Performance Measurement System
PrePCT	Predictor for Position Congestion Tensor
OWENN	Optimal Weight Elman Neural Network
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
LCNN	Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average
RMS	Root Mean Square

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

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This section describe the basics introduction of AI techniques involved in the mapping and prediction over a large dataset. Later covers problem statement, objective of the study, and organization of complete study.

1.1 OVERVIEW

The use of vehicles has increased mobility for human activities, but it has also brought about a number of major problems, including air pollution, excessive fossil fuel use, and traffic congestion, all of which contribute to climate change. Vehicle emissions, which account for a significant portion of urban emissions like CO and NOX and others which significantly contribute to specific PM2.5 concentrations, which have significantly worsened air pollution issues for global megacities.

Also, traffic monitoring in the urban scenario has long been a major topic among academics and industry professionals, with the super-fast expansion of the metropolitan road network and the explosion of automobiles in recent decades, has led to more traffic congestion and hence more vehicular emissions.

Innumerable detectors and sensors have been mounted on fixed sites with short detection ranges in traditional traffic monitoring systems to assist record diverse road conditions and road level traffic emissions across the network. Such systems have a lot of restrictions when it comes to range and efficacy [1-4]. However, the use of Data Science and Artificial intelligence can solve a lot of these issues. Residents' daily lives may be made more pleasant and safe of hazardous pollution by utilizing technological innovation to assist the new experience.

Artificial intelligence can handle significant concerns faced by an increasingly urban population, such as traffic management, healthcare, energy problems, and a variety of other issues and this could also be implemented in real time. So it has the potential to enhance the lives of inhabitants and companies in a smart city.

So the matter of discussion arise what AI is and which components of AI could be used for the traffic congestion problems in the city of New Delhi. So, it is important to understand both of these terms for understanding the work which has been done and will be discussing further.

Artificial Intelligence is an approach to make the machine think and act like humans i.e. making machines intelligent. It is the study of how the brain learns, think, decide and work, during problem-solving. A machine is well trained to perform its action smartly just as the normal human mind do and also taking decisions on its own. Once the machine is trained it does not require any guidance for its work. The main aim is to improve the reasoning, learning, and problem solving of the machines.

The AI consist of two models one is Machine Learning and the other one is Deep Learning. Two models make up the AI. Deep learning and machine learning. Artificial intelligence (AI) employs networks that can take in unsupervised, unstructured, or unlabeled data for deep learning, a subtype of machine learning. Also known as deep neural learning or a deep neural system.

Digit time, which has generated a flood of information in all formats and from every corner of the globe as it has linkages with deep learning. Through techniques like cloud computing, this enormous amount of data is instantaneously available and can be shared in an easy way.

But, the content is frequently unstructured, is so enormous that it may take a long time for individuals to comprehend it and focus on the relevant material Organizations are gradually adapting to AI frameworks for computerised support, seeing the enormous potential that can be realised as a result of unravelling this massive amount of data.

Deep Learning (DL) is a machine learning technique for extracting insights from data, comprehending patterns in data, and classifying, predicting and forecasting data thus as an optimum approach the technologically advance deep learning, data analytics, and communication technologies are being utilised to connect people, roads, and automobiles to solve a range of traffic problems. This programme focuses on several actions targeted at creating a transportation environment that is vehicle-centric, secure, and efficient using the data which is generated.

1.2 MOTIVATION

Traffic management has become an important day-to-day routine in cities today with an unprecedented rise in road traffic. Road organizations have a vital role to play in strengthening organizational and planning practices, as well as providing policymakers with accurate data to be used in making strategic decisions.

With most of the cities using static monitoring devices and practices to determine the traffic congestion on roads and the emissions due to vehicles it becomes difficult to make efficient policy decision for a rapidly changing city like New Delhi.

The use of available tools like google maps to gather real time traffic data and further gain insights for various different use can revolutionise the process of policy making for a city. As this open access data is easily available and could be used to map traffic congestion, further forecast could be done on the same using latest techniques. While a great deal of research has been done, and statistical modelling tools are being used to do forecast of the available data, even though good accuracy and precision has been achieved, but still some gaps been seen in the literature. But in search for a perfect solution with greater precision. DL approaches could be used in order to provide more accuracy on a complex form of dataset automatically.

Thus the above study of the various work has propelled me to contribute my efforts towards this topic and do more research in this field. Moreover, it has given a clear hint to switch to some other Deep Learning Algorithm which will give accurate results.

1.3 PROBLEM OUTLINE

The quality of life in cities is characterized by, how clean its environment is or in other words, what is the level of air pollution in the city. It has been know how chaotic traffic situations can be on city roads which gets amplified by frequent congestions on it hence it is one of the major contributor of air pollution, so the need for systematic prediction of vehicular congestion is a must, for which TCI could be a good indicator. Currently it has been observed that there has been no recent attempt to predict TCI Index for the city of New Delhi. In the given study it has been observed that the vehicular emissions could be analysed based on the TCI index of the respective city.

1.4 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The objective of the dissertation is to first gather the TCI Index dataset for New Delhi and perform prediction and forecasting using LSTM, further prepare a vehicular emission inventory using it. The specific objectives of the studies were:

Objective 1 To Study and analysis of different available prediction and forecasting techniques.

Objective 2 Prepare the dataset of TCI for New Delhi using techniques like web scraping and manually collecting data insights from different available sources.

Objective 3 Exploratory data analysis for identification gaps present in the dataset, so as to maintain constant time series frequency.

Objective 4 Training of the deep learning model over the prepared time series Dataset of TCI using RNN (LSTM) in order to give put predictions.

Objective 5 Converting the TCI Index into dynamic vehicular CO emission inventory for the city of New Delhi.

1.5 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a research method similar to the method proposed by Steven Elsworth [5] to carry the time series prediction using LSTM over the gathered dataset of TCI Index for New Delhi. The data was gathered using various different open source available resources and using techniques like web scraping Once the data was gathered, it was prepared and redundancy was removed in the Unix time stamped data. The collection of such a dataset for the study which trained and tested using an LSTM model to achieve optimum accuracy in prediction. Then the dataset gathered was converted into road level vehicular emission using Indian emission parameters simulating the study conducted by Yifan Wen [6] where dynamic mapping has been done for road level emissions using open access traffic congestion index for the Chinese city of Shenzhen.

Figure 1.1 Research Methodology

1.6 ORGANISATION OF DISSERTATION

Chapter 1: Introduction

The chapter covers an element description of the introduction of AI and Deep Learning which has a crucial role to play in prediction and forecasting. Moving further discuss the problem outline, the objective of the dissertation, motivation, methodology, subject matter and the dissertation's overall structure.

Chapter 2: Study and Review of Literature

This chapter covers literature review techniques LSTM being used for time series prediction as well different ways that were deployed to predict general traffic congestion. Adding over, it also consist of review of different vehicular emissions mapping approached proposed by the researchers have been explained.

Chapter 3: Preliminary Techniques

This chapter covers the introduction of various techniques that have already been proposed before along with the techniques that have been taken in the implementation of the dissertation. Moreover, the chapter gives a brief of all the tools, techniques, language, stats and framework that has been used for the completion of the study.

Chapter 4: Proposed Work

This chapter explains the suggested method employed for preparing of the dataset (TCI Index for the city of New Delhi) and then performing prediction and forecasting over dataset in order to further obtain the road level vehicular emission inventory for the city.

Chapter 5: Results and Discussion

This chapter conducts a thorough analysis of the outcomes of the study's use of LSTM. It also discuss the high resolution vehicular emission inventory that was constructed for the city of New Delhi.

Chapter 6: Conclusions and Future Work

This chapter aims to summarize the dissertation contribution by emphasizing results, importance, and limits of the current research and directions for the future.

CHAPTER 2

STUDY AND REVIEW OF LITERATURE

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In this section, based on the motivation outlined, many research publications have been summarized and used to study various different prediction techniques and different ways to map vehicular pollution of a city.

2.1 INTRODUCTION

In every city's mobility, the city's transport system serves as a lifeline for the smooth running of the city. Life comes to a halt for people living in urban areas whenever a congestion on roads is encountered and people are stuck in traffic jams. The number of vehicles is rapidly increasing on roads and in many areas the road infrastructure has not been able to keep pace with rising number of these vehicles, hence the congestion due to these vehicles has increased rapidly in the cities. This has also resulted in rise in vehicular emissions from them which in turn results in more air pollution in cities. So the need for systematic traffic management and enforcement of laws is a must. In a city build-up, an intelligent transport system is important for the efficient and adaptive control of the transport system. With the idea of cities transmuting into digital communities, making their citizens' lives simpler in every aspect, the Intelligent Transport System is becoming an indispensable component among all. Therefore, the development of a system that could predict and forecast traffic congestion, is crucial for traffic management. The focus is on a particular kind of measurement, namely the traffic congestion index for New Delhi. The study proposes to build an automatic method using AI techniques to map and predict TCI Index and prepare a dynamic vehicular emission inventory. But every model and algorithm has some limitations. Researchers are doing a lot in this field to make algorithms more accurate and efficient.

2.2 RELATED WORK

The continuous tracking and evaluation of a traffic scene are essential for a variety of applications, including surveillance, traffic control, and rescue tasks. Traffic congestion mapping and prediction and then converting it into vehicular emission.

But on the other hand, it is a tough challenge due to a variety of factors, including vehicle size, different types of vehicles and their variety in terms of the orientations, varying to different regions as, different countries and cities have different emission norms, which researchers must consider.

Despite all the other previous research work in this field a lot of researchers have still not been able to implement it in different cities of the world. Researchers are still working on deep learning to come up with a model with better accuracy.

Anita Yadava [15] One of the most popular deep learning models nowadays is called Long Short Term Memory (LSTM). As a result of long-term trends, seasonal and cyclical oscillations, and random noise, it is also used to predict time series, which is a particularly challenging task to solve. A number of hyper-parameters must be carefully chosen in order to get good results which are crucial to achieve success of LSTM. Being such a fresh idea, there aren't any established guidelines for configuring LSTM. In order to fill this research gap, a dataset from the Indian Stock Market was constructed, and an LSTM model was developed for it. This model was then further improved by comparing two distinct models, namely stateless and stateful models, by adjusting the hidden layers. Stateful and stateless LSTMs were examined for four companies—ICICI, TCS, Reliance, and Maruti—in the two experiments that were undertaken. According to their P-values, the differences between stateful and stateless LSTM for the experiment's chosen stock price prediction problem were statistically insignificant. The majority of the variations in results were caused by the random seeding that occurs for each LSTM run and resulting in minute variations in output. Stateless had a smaller deviation or spread than stateful, as seen by the box and whisker plot graphic's standard deviation figures and spread. As a consequence, stateless LSTM seems to be more stable than stateful LSTM according to their results, which demonstrate that a stateless LSTM model is preferred for time series prediction challenges due to its higher stability. In Experiment 2, there were one to seven layers that were hidden. The results show that $n = 1$ appears to be the best configuration based on their mean RMSE. According to the experimental results, a stateless LSTM model and one hidden layer were sufficient to get the best results on their Indian dataset.

S. Narmadha [20] As traffic congestion is a significant issue in both developed and developing nations, this study proposed hybrid neural network techniques such as Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) networks for short term traffic flow prediction based on multivariate analysis. In order to reduce traffic and increase vehicle flow, traffic management systems are designed to eliminate instability and accidents. Advanced Traffic Information Systems (ATIS), Advanced Traffic Management Systems (ATMS), and traffic analytics will all be helpful in controlling traffic congestion. Vehicle congestion during peak hours is influenced by non-linear historical data and unpredictable circumstances, which cannot be taken into account by current algorithms. In order to incorporate many components including total flow, weather, and precipitation as well as the extraction of the spatial and temporal characteristics of upstream and downstream stations, a hybrid model comprising a convolutional neural network and a long short term memory network was utilised. A multilayer auto encoder was used to fill in the missing values in the traffic and meteorological data (SDAE). Both CNN and LSTM have been employed and have demonstrated their ability to integrate a wide range of components. CNN extracts spatial information from upstream and downstream stations, while LSTM extracts time-sensitive data from adjacent stations. The multivariate analysis has only used data from a single time step. Using sensors and loop detectors, data on traffic, weather, and precipitation were gathered. The Performance Measurement System (PeMS), a database that collects traffic-related data from 44,734 sensors spread across California, was used to collect traffic statistics. Every 30 seconds, data was gathered and condensed into 5-minute periods. The model was trained for 50 epochs in order to achieve better results. With the use of this dataset, it was discovered that the CNN-LSTM Hybrid prediction model outperforms other models in terms of accuracy.

Mengting Bai [19] In this study it has been proposed, a Predictor for Position Congestion Tensor in addition to it a model called Relative Position Congestion Tensor for prediction of traffic congestion was also created. In first stage, a unique method for constructing congestion matrices on region oriented traffic networks based on the concept of relative node positions and then transforming matrices into spatio-temporal tensors.

Then, a method for foreseeing congestion in all areas of the road network in the near future was given utilising a convolutional long-short memory network. The results of the experiments conducted have demonstrated that the proposed method performs better than standard models such as Linear Regression, Long-Short Term Memory, Random Forest, Gradient Boosting Regression, Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average, and Convolution-based deep Neural Network modelling Periodic traffic data in all areas where congestion is common. In order to anticipate congestion, research was also conducted to assess the interpretability of the underlying structure of the Predictor for Position Congestion Tensor model. Their findings show that, when compared to the baseline models, the proposed model PrePCT has the highest accuracy. PrePCT can accurately predict traffic network congestion for the upcoming 30 minutes.

S. Neelakandan [14] The OWENN algorithm and an Intel 80,286 CPU were used in this research to demonstrate an effective IoT-based traffic prediction and traffic light management system for a smart city. IoT data collection, feature extraction, categorization, optimised traffic IoT values, and traffic signal control system were the five steps that made up the whole study. It begins by gathering IoT traffic data from the dataset, after which it retrieves traffic, weather, and direction data. These qualities are then put into the OWENN classifier, which identifies the place with the greatest traffic. If one route via the website receives more traffic than the other, IBSO was used to optimise the IoT values, and an Intel 80,286 CPU finally took over management of the traffic. The categorization was completed once these features were extracted. The areas with the greatest traffic in the area were classified using the optimal weight Elman neural network (OWENN) method. OWENN outperformed the prior model in terms of accuracy, achieving 98.23% and a 96.69% F-score. According to the results of their studies, it has been indicated that this system works better than cutting-edge methodologies.

Yifan Wena [6] The primary goal of this study was to improve the intelligence and accuracy of vehicle emission control in the Chinese city of Shenzhen. From this study, a novel method for building high-resolution traffic emission inventories has been developed that may be applied to a variety of cities, especially those with data shortages.

Using the open-access traffic congestion index, a generated a high-resolution emission inventory of hourly fluxes of air pollutants and carbon dioxide from on-road vehicles along the whole road network in Shenzhen, China. The Shenzhen central business district was taken and observed during rush hours. Fine-grained quantification of "excess" emissions from rush-hour traffic was conducted, with varied emission enhancement (14.3–30.4 percent) for different pollutants and "excess" consumption of gasoline and diesel at rates of 24.3–26.8 percent and 19.6–22.0 percent, respectively. When the impacts of freight operations on pollutant emissions were assessed, it was discovered that heavy-duty trucks were responsible for up to 50% of the total emissions of nitrogen oxides, fine particulate matter, and carbon dioxide at the street level. This cataloguing allowed for the creation of the city's high resolution traffic emission inventory.

Jigu Seo [25] In this study, a road vehicle emission model that integrates an artificial neural network (ANN) model with a vehicle dynamics model was used to estimate the instantaneous carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), and total hydrocarbon (THC) emissions of diesel light-duty vehicles. Using actual measurement data, a multi-layer feed-forward ANN model was developed. The optimal mix of the several experimental elements was selected as the ANN input through a parametric study that took into account both practicality and accuracy. In order to develop an adequate ANN model for CO₂ prediction, utilization of two variables was needed (engine speed and engine torque). The integrated model is practical since it just needed a few fundamental pieces of information, including vehicle characteristics, speed, and road grade. During accuracy validation, the model that was created showed excellent prediction accuracy for road vehicle emissions. To achieve sufficient accuracy for CO and NO_x prediction, more variables were included in ANN training. The integrated model is practical since it only needs a few simple input variables, including vehicle characteristics, speed, and road grade. For road vehicle emissions, the model showed high forecast accuracy.

2.3 CHAPTER SUMMARY

The review of all prior research in the area of vehicle detection and counting was addressed in this chapter. It precisely covers every ML and DL approach. From the study and examination of the literature, it can be deduced that although some strategies worked well, others weren't quite up to par. Others lag in a different region while some achieve higher precision but fail to execute in real-time. The analysis of the many works discussed above has motivated me to give my time and energy to this subject, conduct further research, and become an expert in this area. Additionally, it has clearly shown that switching to a different Deep Learning algorithm that will perform better at object identification, as well as processing speed, and be able to execute in a real-time scenario is necessary. In the following chapter, all the preliminary techniques that are used for the implementation of the objective have been described.

CHAPTER 3

PRELIMINARY TECHNIQUES

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3.1 INTRODUCTION

The vast bulk of which has been included into stats modeling like ARIMA, Deep Learning, Neural Networks and a variety of other computed algorithms. Those works have clearly defined how advancement in technology could be used to unravel the power of data to make forecast, which will in turn help in improving overall efficiency of the system and make life healthier and better.

In this chapter, we'll discuss all the techniques, methodologies, algorithms and implementation frameworks including all the functional dependencies that have been required to carry out the study for the city of New Delhi.

The chapter will first provide an introduction to the conceptual approach for Machine Learning, Deep Learning, RNN, LSTM n that has been implemented to make study more efficient. Moving forward, all of the implementation tools and framework that were needed to complete the dissertation have been briefly described, along with their contribution to the dissertation.

The goal is to create a time series prediction model using LSTM which could predict the TCI Index for the city of New Delhi at every hour, during the study period.

3.2 CONCEPTUAL APPROACH

3.2.1 Machine Learning

In today's world, machine learning is extensively used. Instead of directly programming computer applications, machine learning is used to train them.[10] Rather than being explicitly coded, a machine-learning system is trained by humans. It is given a massive number of task-specific instances, which it analyses for statistical structure, allowing the system to generate rules for automating the work. To automate the process of labelling your holiday photos, for example, a machine-learning framework with a huge number of tests [10] could be used. Machine Learning also plays a vital role in automating forecasting techniques as using it has improved the accuracy levels over the earlier used statistical modeling techniques.

Let's look at a child's learning as an example. He/she learns with the support of his/her parents and teachers. We're concentrating on the child's learning style. The teacher and parent provide a set of examples for the youngster to grasp and educate his minds, such as alphabets, numerals, and other symbols. This is a practical demonstration of how a machine learning algorithm operates. To construct a good machine learning model, we'll also need several samples.

As previously mentioned, machine learning employs mathematical rules and various algorithms to perform data processing tasks. Three things are being done to perform machine learning task.

Input data point:- in order to predict Pneumonia, then the input data point could be the x-ray images. Or if the task is object detection, the input data point could be the pictures.

Example of the expected output:- In the pneumonia detection, there could be output which is tagged as “pneumonia positive” and “pneumonia negative”. In object detection, expected output could be tagged as “man”, “woman”, “table”, “chair” and so on.

Measuring the algorithm that the algorithm is providing a good result or not:- The first need is to find the difference between actual output and expected output which is very necessary. There is some set of formulae used to calculate the difference. This calculation provides feedback that allows to fine-tune the algorithm's operation. The whole processing is known as learning.

We are providing a set of examples that are known as a dataset. The machine learning model takes the dataset as input and train model using train set and dev set and predict output for any task. Any machine learning model says to be good because its prediction and the actual result are approximately the same.

There are three machine learning algorithms. Supervised learning in which machine learning algorithms are applied, on the labelled dataset and try to predict the outcome based on the known features. The second is unsupervised learning in which data is unlabeled and tries to group data points based on their similarity. And third is Reinforcement learning in which the model learns to act as experience.

But machine learning has some limitation that, It cannot solve crucial AI problem such as NLP, image recognition. The machine learning algorithm cannot deal with the high dimensionality of the dataset. If the dataset is large then it is difficult to apply a machine learning algorithm It is extremely difficult for machine learning to solve complicated tasks like object identification and handwriting recognition.

3.2.2 Deep Learning

The deep learning method overcomes the limitations of the machine learning system. In deep learning, the word "deep" refers to the concept of learning. The representation of data (and the features) is not easily defined in certain cases and for more complex problems, particularly where the features are likely to be high-level and abstract. Deep learning is a technique that helps computers to understand more complex concepts by describing them in terms of their relationships with simpler concepts, resulting in a multi-layered hierarchy. A vast number of densely linked computational pieces make up an artificial neural network (ANN), which works together to solve issues.

In simple words, Deep learning uses the concept of the human brain such as how different neurons are connected, how passing of information from one neuron to another neuron is taking place. Let's take an example by which to understand the working of neural networks. Suppose there is 5 ant. Together the ants may pick something. The ants can't, however, establish an anthill or collaborate as a large group. At the same moment, there are a swarm of ants everywhere. These ants can construct the entire ant colony. These ants can also construct an anthill. As a result, a large number of neurons working together to create magic.

Deep learning used today in computer vision, in medicine or it can be used for business problems or for a computer vision problem like recognizing faces and pictures or video or even recognizing tumor in some brain images and it is also used in some recommended system with the use of deep Boltzmann machine. So basically all the neurons that are on the first layer where all the signal coming to those neurons.

Therefore, the hidden layer, a processing component of the network that gives additional information to the output layer, receives the signal from the input layer neuron. With this analogy, if the talk is about the human brain, the input layer is sense organs means whatever a person can see, hear, feel, touch or smell. The human brain is getting only electrical impulse, which is coming from these organs such as the ear, eyes, nose, etc. In the case of deep learning, these are the input values that are the independent variable. Your input value is passed through the synapse to the hidden layer and then the output value is passed further.

Since all of these independent variables are for a single observation, a person may think of them as a single row in your dataset. All descriptions of a single individual that your model either uses to train itself or those are used to make predictions based on the input value. Output value could not be one there will be several output variable which will be representing your categories. When the artificial neural network is being trained. Essentially, you're changing the weights in all of the synapses around the entire network.

The activation function is a function ascribed to the neuron or the layer as a whole. Input signal either pass through it or not pass through it that is depends on the functionality of the activation function there are some activation function such as threshold activation function, sigmoid activation function, tangent activation function, rectifier function.

It is a step-wise process.

Step 1: Set the weight to a small number very near to zero at random (but not zero).

Step 2: Put the first observation of your dataset, one feature per input node in the input.

Step 3: Propagating it forward: The neurons get activated sequentially from left to right, with the effect of each neuron's activation that is limited by the weights that are used to propagate to the activation till the desired outcome is achieved.

Step 4: Compare all of the desired outcomes to the actual outcomes.

Step 5: backpropagation: The effect is propagated backwards from right to left. Update the weight based on how much of them are responsible for the mistake, that how often the weight is updated is determined by the learning rate.

Step 6: Rep stages 1–5 with the weight updated after each observation, or repeat steps 1–5 with the weight updated only after a batch of observations.

Step 7: ANN has processed the entire training set that is known as an epoch. More epochs should be done so that the model's accuracy improves and it functions properly.

3.2.3 Recurrent Neural Network

Yann LeCun introduced a convolutional neural network in 1998. RNNs may process input sequences utilising their internal state, in contrast to feedforward neural networks (memory). As a result, tasks like speech recognition and unsegmented, connected handwriting recognition are feasible. In other neural networks, each input operates independently of the others.

However, with an RNN, every input is linked to every other input. RNNs may process input sequences utilising their internal state, in contrast to feedforward neural networks (memory). As a result, tasks like speech recognition and unsegmented, connected handwriting recognition are feasible. In other neural networks, each input operates independently of the others. But with an RNN, every input is linked to every other input.

Figure 3.1 RNN Working

It initially takes x_0 out of the string of inputs before creating h_0 , which in addition with x_1 , is used as, input for the next stage. Consequently, h_1 and x_0 are the inputs for the next phase (1). Similar to this, the input for the subsequent stage is h_1 , followed by x_2 for the following step, and so on. It retains the context as a consequence throughout training.

The equation for the present situation is as follows:

$$h_t = f(h_{t-1}, x_t) \quad \dots (3.1)$$

We apply the function of activation:

$$h_f = \tan h(W_{hh}h_{t-1} + W_{xh}x_t) \quad \dots (3.2)$$

W_{xh} is the weight at the current input state, W_{hh} is the weight at the previous hidden state, and \tanh is the function of activation. \tanh implements a non-linearity that will squash the range of activation to $[-1, 1]$.

Output: The state of output is Y_t . The output state weight is at W_{hy} .

$$Y_t = W_{hy}h_t \quad \dots (3.3)$$

3.2.4 Long Short Term Memory

Long Short-Term Memory networks might be referred to as RNN expansions, because it expands the memory of recurrent neural networks. An RNN is referred to as an LSTM network since the structural units for its layers are LSTMs. RNNs can recall the contributions of LSTMs over a lengthy period of time thanks to LSTMs. The information is kept in LSTMs memory, which can read, write, and erase data, making it comparable to a computer's memory. The LSTM is a neural network that is still in development. In any case, it has cycled in the neuron connections, which is not the same as a fully linked neural network.

The effects of temporary memory are vulnerable to RNNs. Transmitting data from previous time stages to later ones if a series is quite long would face some trouble. As a result, if you're trying to predict something from a long stretch of text, RNNs could leave out critical information. The LSTM was created to solve the problem of transitory memory. As it had the feature of internal mechanism called gates that can control the flow of data. These gates can choose which information in an arrangement should be kept and which should be discarded. It can then transfer relevant data down the long chain of events in order to develop projections.

Let's say there is need to buy a life cereal and we're checking for reviews online. We'll read the survey first, then determine whether it was appropriate and when a review is read, the human brain only remembers the important words.

People probably don't remember the word as people don't care about terms like "give," "ate," "this," and so on.

In addition, that is essentially what an LSTM accomplishes. It can find out how to store just relevant data in order to produce forecasts, and it doesn't recall irrelevant data. The phrases which are remembered helped to decide that it was okay in this scenario.

Figure 3.2 LSTM Working

Inputs	
X_t	Input Vector
C_{t-1}	Memory from previous block

Table 3.1 Inputs

Outputs	
C_t	Current Block Memory
h_t	Current Block Output
h_{t-1}	Previous block Output

Table 3.2 Outputs

Non-linearity	
s	Input Vector
tanh	Previous Block Memory

Table 3.3 Non-linearities

Vector Operation	
X	Element wise Multiplication
+	Element wise Concatenation
0	Bias

Table 3.4 Vector Operation

A typical LSTM network consists of a number of memory segments called cells. The cell state as well as the hidden state are both passed to the next cell. Memory cells are in charge of recalling information, and three key qualities known as gates regulate access to this memory. Each of the gates are explained further.

- **Forget Gate**

To begin, forget gate is given. This gate decides whether or not data should be saved or erased.

- The gate is recipient of data from two sources: h_{t-1} and x_t .
- The source, x_t , is the contribution made at that specific time step, and h_{t-1} is the yield or concealed state from the preceding cell. The weight matrices are multiplied by the chosen data sources, and a bias is then applied. Then, this value is determined using the sigmoid method. Data from both the previous and present covered states are analysed using the sigmoid method.
- The result of the qualities was somewhere between 0 and 1. The value that is closer to 0 should be disregarded, while the value that is closer to 1 should be maintained.

- **Input Gate**

The input gate is in charge of adding data to the state of the cell. This data addition is essentially a process of three steps.

- The esteems that should be added to the cell state is controlled using a sigmoid function. This works in the same way as the forget gate, acting as a route for all of the data from h_{t-1} and x_t .
- Creating a vector with every possible characteristic that may be added to the cell state (as seen in h_{t-1} and x_t). This is performed using the tanh approach, which yields numbers ranging from - 1 to +1.
- Adding this crucial data to the cell state via addition activity after multiplying the value of the regulatory channel (the sigmoid gate) by the made-up vector (the tanh capacity).

- **Output Gate**

Finally, there's the output gate. The output gate determines the true state of the following disguised state. Keep in mind that the concealed unit holds data from earlier inputs. The concealed state is often used to make predictions.

- To begin, a sigmoid algorithm is used to feed the previous hidden state and the current input. The tanh method receives the newly changed cell state. The sigmoid production is multiplied by the tanh yield to decide what data the disguised state should communicate. The yield is a condition that goes unobserved.
- The hidden condition and particular cell condition are subsequently carried over to the following time step. In this section the input, forget, and output gates' equations are represented by i_t , f_t , and O_t , respectively, while the weights are represented by w and the sigmoid function is represented as σ :

$$\begin{aligned} i_t &= \sigma (w_i [x_t, h_{t-1}] + b_i) \\ f_t &= \sigma (w_f [x_t, h_{t-1}] + b_f) \\ O_t &= \sigma (w_o [x_t, h_{t-1}] + b_o) \end{aligned} \quad \dots (3.4)$$

3.2.5 Model Optimization

The feature detector matrix is also updated in order to improve performance the following time. The inaccuracies multiply every time feature detectors are altered, weights are modified, and this entire process is repeated. The network is optimised in this way. A neural network learns its data in this manner. However, what matters most in this case is that the data covers the entire piece from beginning to end. The inaccuracy is then measured, estimated, and then propagated once again. There are several techniques for improving the weights in the neural network to improve the model. I'd want to mention what changes are necessary for the learning rate. It will subtract it from the previous output value, which is where the updated value is received, as part of the output. A suitable gradient cannot be utilised if the dataset is too large since it is time-consuming and will become trapped at the local optimum.

3.2.5.1 Gradient Descent

An iterative optimization technique is the gradient descent algorithm. This method is being used to find a differential function for the the local optimum. Think about the scenario where someone is at the top of a hill and wants to go to the river on the other side. The individual should descend farther till it reaches the minimum point every time it descends to reach the objective person.

$$j(\theta_0, \theta_1) = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{i=1}^m [h_{\theta}(x_i) - y_i]^2$$

$$\theta_j = \theta_j - \alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_j} j(\theta_0, \theta_1) \quad \dots (3.5)$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} j_{\theta} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{i=1}^m [h_{\theta}(x_i) - y]^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (h_{\theta}(x_i) - y) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_j} (\theta x_i - y) \\ &= \frac{1}{m} (h_{\theta}(x_i) - y) x_i \end{aligned} \quad \dots (3.6)$$

Therefore,

$$\theta_{f.} = \theta_j - \frac{\alpha}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m [(h_{\theta}(x_i) - y) x_i] \quad \dots (3.7)$$

Where x_i is the projected value, y_i is the real value, and α is the learning rate

When the backpropagation phase is present, gradient descent enters the picture. Measure the error delta at this point, and then begin backpropagation from the top layer to return to the propagation step. Calculating the number of modifications necessary to obtain the partial function derivative with respect to w .

Stochastic Gradient Descent:

Use the stochastic gradient descent approach when a dataset is sufficiently large. Dealing with a random probability in the stochastic technique. As a result, it only addresses a small portion of the large dataset rather than the complete dataset. Instead of summing the gradients of the cost functions of all the examples in the gradient descent, the stochastic gradient descent algorithm assists in finding the cost function at each iteration for a single example.

3.2.5.2 Adam Optimizer

Adam analyzer strategy for versatile learning rate advancement that is utilized rather than the stochastic slope drop. It's anything but a blend of RMSprop and Stochastic slope plunge with force. It's anything but a versatile rate of learning approach since it estimated singular rate of learning for various boundaries.

The first and second inclination minutes, by which learning rates are accepted for each weight of the neural organisation, are used by the Adam analyzer. Adam Enhancer is the best analyser employed to prepare the 3D convolutional neural structure in this model since it is anything but a flexible learning rate technique.

3.3 IMPLEMENTATIONAL TOOLS**3.3.1 Python 3.0**

Python is an extensively used high-level computer language for general-purpose programming. It supports procedural and object-oriented paradigms. The whole dissertation has been implemented using the python code.

3.3.2 Jupyter Notebook

Jupyter notebooks are a form of an interactive computing environment that may be used to develop Python-based data science applications. Jupyter notebooks organise materials like code, images, text, and performance to display the analytical process in depth. It assists a data scientist in documenting while working on analysis in a stepwise approach. Using Jupyter notebooks, it is easy to share the work with a peer. The analysis part of the study has been carried out in the jupyter notebook.

3.3.3 TensorFlow

A high-performance numerical computing open-source software programme is called TensorFlow. Deep learning and machine learning applications are created with it. The Google team created TensorFlow to construct and research fascinating artificial intelligence concepts. TensorFlow is a user-friendly application since it is developed in the Python programming language.

3.3.4 Keras

Open-source neural network library Keras runs on Theano or Tensorflow and is based on Python. It is designed to be flexible, fast, and easy to use. On top of TensorFlow, Keras is a deep learning framework with built-in modules for all neural network calculations. For study implementation, Keras have been used.

3.4 CHAPTER SUMMARY

In this chapter, the description discusses the technology, techniques, and algorithms employed in the creation of the suggested work. The intended work implementation portion and how it turned out to be overcoming the deficiencies that have been highlighted in the first chapters of the dissertation have been detailed in the next chapter, which is based on the approach stated above.

CHAPTER 4

PROPOSED WORK

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4.4	Carbon Monoxide Emission Inventory Conversion.....	33
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4.1 INTRODUCTION

Proposed scheme is focusing on novel approach for the prediction of TCI Index for the city of New Delhi and the subsequent mapping of vehicular emissions using it for the city. From all the previous work that's been carried out in the field, It has been observed that there hasn't been an attempt to forecast TCI of New Delhi using LSTM approach, also there haven't been a study where TCI Index of the city of New Delhi is being used to map vehicular emissions for the city.

The flow of the chapter starts with a discussion of the dataset and then goes into detail about the proposed methodology. As a result, the research's structure and strategy will be thoroughly explained in this chapter to address the research topic.

4.2 DATASET

For the input, the data was collected by the process of web scraping from the website [17]. The organization calculates the TCI Index data using google maps, the web application is built over the top of the traffic layer within the google maps. The layer specified uses four colour coded lines to represent traffic congestion i.e.: green, red, orange, and dark-red. The shade of the colour represents the congestion levels, the darker the colour more the congestion.

The web software saves a picture for each tracked location every 20 minutes, comprising traffic statistics from Google Maps. The data is represented in the form of line graph, at every twenty minutes of frequency, and the time was denoted using Unix timestamp, which is a kind of a number consisting all the details of the exact time as well as date. In order to compute the values of the TCI Index they were using the photos were studied for a few minutes, and the percentages of the four traffic hues i.e. green, red, orange, and dark-red which represent the amount of congestion on city roads are computed, which are then all added together further processed to compute final TCI Index of the city.

4.3 TCI INDEX PREDICTION MODEL

The work is executed in three phases:

- Phase 1: Data handling so that it can be feed to the LSTM model.
- Phase 2: Deals with the training neural networks and model optimization.

In the below Figure execution flow of the proposed work has been depicted.

Figure 4.1 Execution Flow of Vehicle Classification and Evaluation model

4.3.1 DATA HANDLING

Data handling is the first and most important stage in implementing any model. It is considered as the base of a hypothetical structure. The dataset is produced in this first stage from the previous step. An.csv file containing the data is created by web scraping. After that, this dataset must be given into the build model in order to train it. Therefore, it is crucial to handle the dataset first before feeding it to the model for training. The accuracy of the models will gradually rise as a result. Data collecting, Data Pre-processing, and Data Visualization are the three most important processes that often make up this phase of data handling.

4.3.1.1 Data Gathering

Before beginning to train any model, this is the most important stage. Collecting a dataset from diverse sources is necessary in the initial phase. It is crucial to bear in mind that data should be gathered from a reliable source while developing deep learning and machine learning applications.

4.3.1.2 Data Pre-Processing

Pre-processing is a technique for transforming raw data into something the model can use. Always utilize clean, properly structured data while working on the model. As a result, the preprocessing phase formats the data for later usage. The real data is typically not well structured and frequently contains defects that make it inappropriate to be fed to models, such as bugs, missing values, trash values, and multiple mistakes. Consequently, the pre-processing stage is necessary to create data on the point that will be utilised in the model, enhancing efficiency. Most of the time, the pre-processing step focuses on discovering missing value, inconsistent value, and duplicate value. In the dataset, available data had many missing points in between it, which was hampering the data consistency and its frequency. So, in order to make the data consistent the time series data was first converted into Indian standard time from, Unix timestamp and then the discrepancies were removed manually by entering relevant data into the dataset. The resultant dataset had a frequency of 20 minutes.

I.e. TCI index was recorded at a gap of every 20 minutes. But for study the data was used at a frequency of every 60 minutes.

4.3.1.3 Data Visualization and Data split Data Visualization

When conveyed visually rather than textually, often heard ideas are simpler to understand. The same philosophy underlies data visualisation. Data visualisation involves displaying data in a graphical way to identify trends and reveal incredibly insightful information.

Data Split

Data splitting divides the given dataset into two pieces only for the purpose of cross-validation. The other component is used to assess the model's performance while the first part is used as a prediction model.

4.3.2 MODEL TRAINING

4.3.2.1 Training Neural Network

To train the LSTM neural network the data set would be first preprocessed by normalizing of the dataset then the data set would be sliced in the ratio of 1225:120 i.e. 1225 for the training and 120 for testing the predicted values. The training dataset would be then scaled using a MinmaxScaler and further would undergo a scaler transformation in order to make the data points in a uniform order. Then the LSTM model would be built by using a sequential model with one layer of LSTM and three layers of dense and would be utilising the relu activation function with Adam as the optimizer which would allow to train the build model. In order to avoid overfitting, the model would be trained for the course of 100 epochs.

Figure 4.2 Neural Network Training

Adam Optimizer

Instead of the stochastic slope drop, the Adam analyzer technique for flexible learning rate advancement is used. RMSprop and the stochastic slope fall with force are everything but blended. Since it calculated the solitary learning rate for different borders, it is anything but a flexible learning rate technique. The first and second inclination minutes, by which learning rates are accepted for each weight of the neural organisation, are used by the Adam analyzer. Adam Enhancer is the best analyser employed to prepare neural structure in this model since it is anything but a flexible learning rate technique.

4.4 CARBON MONOXIDE EMISSIONS INVENTORY CONVERSION

The TCI index dataset which would prepared would be used to create a high definition CO vehicular emission inventory for the city of New Delhi. The inventory would be prepared simulating a similar study which was conducted for the Chinese city of Shenzhen [6] using Indian parameters and emission norms. The study [6] proposed an equation using which the TCI index could be converted into vehicular emission inventory.

$$E_{p,h,l} = \sum_g (EF_{0,p,g}(v) \times L_1 \times F_{g,h,l}) \quad \dots (4.1)$$

In the equation $E_{p,h,l}$ represents the overall traffic vehicular emissions (in g/h) of the harmful pollutant p during the hour h over link l; $EF_{0,p,g}(v)$ represents the average emission factor (g/km) of the harmful pollutant p for a specific vehicle group g, which is reliant on the link-level hourly speed v (km/h); L_1 represents the length of the total link l (km); and $F_{g,h,l}$ represents the Vehicle group g's hour-hour traffic volume on connection l (veh/h) which is represented by the TCI Index.

The equation 4.1 would be used in order to create the inventory for the city.

- The vehicular traffic would be divided into four sub groups for which the emission norms are standardized and then an average values of emissions would be taken from [18]. The values range for different emission norms which were enforced in India over the time period. The study would only considered the stages of BS 3, BS 4 and BS 6 while the emission inventory would being constructed as the laws don't permit vehicles older than 15 years from plying on the road of New Delhi. This will give the required parameter of average emission factor (in g/km) of the harmful pollutant p for a vehicle group g. The total no. of vehicles plying on New Delhi roads were estimated based on the data published in Delhi Economic Survey report for the year 2021-2022 [27]. In which it was published that the total number of vehicles registered in New Delhi are 1,22,53,350 for the year 2021 and based on an estimated growth of 3.03% annually the number of registered vehicles for the year 2022 in New Delhi are 1,26,33,204.

Number of Vehicles			
Details	2019-20	2020-21	2021-2022
Cars and Jeeps	33,11,579	33,84,736	34,89,663
two wheelers	79,59,753	82,39,550	84,94,976
Ambulance	2,287	2,289	2,360
Auto rickshaw	1,14,891	1,14,869	1,18,430
Taxies	1,22,476	1,12,401	1,15,885
Buses	33,302	33,294	34,326
Other Passenger vehicles	85,477	91,887	94,735
Tractors, Goods (all type)	2,63,112	2,74,324	2,82,828
Total	1,18,92,877	1,22,53,350	1,26,33,204

Table 4.1 Number of Vehicles

- The total road length of Delhi would be taken from the data published in Delhi Economic Survey report for the year 2021-2022 [27] in order to obtain value of variable L in the equation [4.1].
- The value of variable $F_{g,h,l}$ would be obtained from the TCI Index dataset and would be further modified based on the vehicular group based on their density.

4.5 CHAPTER SUMMARY

In this chapter, the feature of deep learning i.e. LSTM, has been described followed by Dataset and System Model and then the conversion model of TCI index into CO vehicular emissions. It explains the implementation mechanism incorporated for the study in detail.

CHAPTER 5

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1	Introduction.....	37
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5.1 INTRODUCTION

Proposed scheme is focusing on predicting the TCI Index for the city of New Delhi. From the approach that was taken, it was successfully able to predict the TCI Index of New Delhi with a good model accuracy.

The flow of the chapter starts with a discussion of the result that has been evaluated in the form of accuracy curves and graphs and will further move on to the graphs of emissions which have been derived from the TCI Index and then moving to the conclusion and a summary. Thus in this chapter, will cover the result and discussion portion of the dissertation.

5.2 RESULT AND ANALYSIS

The dataset which was made was visualized in a graphical format over a time period of 8 weeks having a frequency of 60 minutes, which resulted in 1345 data points.

Figure 5.1 Line Graph of Dataset

In the line graph plotted in Figure 5.1, the x axis represents the time as Unix timestamp and the y axis represents the TCI index of the city of New Delhi over a period of 8 weeks. I.e. from Friday, February 25, 2022 11:36:00 PM IST to Friday, April 22, 2022 11:56:00 PM IST.

The significant depression visible in the graph represents the time of the festival of Holi which had holiday time of 3 days where the traffic on roads of New Delhi decreased significantly. The usual trend observed by the graph was seen that during the morning and the evening peak hours the TCI index goes to its maximum levels and the opposite during late nights.

The implementation for training model, in order to achieve prediction results was done using a uni-variable variant of the LSTM learning model. To train the build model, a sequential model was build having one layer of LSTM and 3 layer of dense using the relu activation function and the optimizer used was adam. The model was trained for a total of 100 epochs so as to prevent overfitting.

```

model = Sequential()
model.add(LSTM(319, activation='relu', input_shape=(n_input, n_features)))
model.add(Dense(32,activation='relu'))
model.add(Dense(32,activation='relu'))
model.add(Dense(1, activation='linear'))
model.compile(optimizer='adam', loss='mse')

```

Figure 5.2 Snip of Code of Model

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
lstm_2 (LSTM)	(None, 319)	409596
dense_6 (Dense)	(None, 32)	10240
dense_7 (Dense)	(None, 32)	1056
dense_8 (Dense)	(None, 1)	33
=====		
Total params: 420,925		
Trainable params: 420,925		
Non-trainable params: 0		

Figure 5.3 LSTM Model Summary

```
1105/1105 [=====] - 75s 67ms/step - loss: 0.0067
Epoch 90/100
1105/1105 [=====] - 75s 68ms/step - loss: 0.0066
Epoch 91/100
1105/1105 [=====] - 75s 68ms/step - loss: 0.0066
Epoch 92/100
1105/1105 [=====] - 76s 69ms/step - loss: 0.0066
Epoch 93/100
1105/1105 [=====] - 75s 68ms/step - loss: 0.0066
Epoch 94/100
1105/1105 [=====] - 75s 68ms/step - loss: 0.0067
Epoch 95/100
1105/1105 [=====] - 76s 68ms/step - loss: 0.0067
Epoch 96/100
1105/1105 [=====] - 75s 68ms/step - loss: 0.0066
Epoch 97/100
1105/1105 [=====] - 75s 68ms/step - loss: 0.0064
Epoch 98/100
1105/1105 [=====] - 75s 68ms/step - loss: 0.0063
```

Figure 5.4 Epoch Training

Loss Curve:

A Loss curve is the most widely used charts to debug a neural network during the time of training. It gives an overview of the training process as well as the learning trajectory of the network. The loss function is computed over all data items during an epoch and ensures that the quantitative loss measure is delivered at that epoch. Visualizing the curve over iterations, on the other hand, only reveals the loss for a subset of the complete dataset.

Figure 5.5 Loss Function Curve

In the loss curve graph, plotted in Figure 5.5 loss per epoch has been represented achieved during the training of the model. In which the x axis denotes the number of epochs and the y axis denotes MSE loss values per epoch.

Accuracy Curve:

Another typical curve used to analyse the growth of Neural Networks is the Accuracy curve. Anyone who has dealt with Deep Learning is familiar with the concepts of accuracy and loss curves. It is more important to consider the curve that contains both training and validation accuracy.

In the below graph, the x axis denotes the time as Unix timestamp and the y axis represents the TCI index of the city of New Delhi.

Figure 5.6 Prediction Cross Validation Graph

The graph in Figure 5.6 represents the cross validation results which were achieved, the blue line represents TCI index which is the real dataset of 120 data points which were sliced from the initial dataset as test. The orange line as TCI2 represents the predicted values of the LSTM model which has been developed. The model explained above has successfully able to identify the trend in the dataset.

CO Vehicular Emission inventory Conversion:

The vehicular emission inventory was made over hourly fluxes over the whole road network for the city of New Delhi. The results were obtained by using the TCI Index of the dataset which was used in the study for the prediction LSTM model and converting the same in CO emissions.

Figure 5.6 CO Emission Inventory Area Graph

The Figure 5.6 is the graphical representation CO Emissions of vehicles in New Delhi during the period of the study. i.e. from Friday, February 25, 2022 11:36:00 PM IST to Friday, April 22, 2022 11:56:00 PM IST, the x axis of the graph represents the time as Unix timestamp and the y axis represents the corresponding CO emissions in (g/h).

5.3 CHAPTER SUMMARY

This chapter does an in-depth analysis on the results obtained after the Prediction and mapping approach taken up in *chapter 4*. The Results are always a good indication of accomplishments. These results are also indicating that the research methodology taken up was able to successfully able to predict the trend has been able to prepare CO vehicular emission inventory for the city of New Delhi. Thus the suggested approaches are successful and can be used further.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

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6.1 INTRODUCTION

The main aim of the study revolves around the prediction of TCI index for the city of New Delhi and then preparing a vehicular CO emission inventory for the city during the period of study. After doing various study and review various methods have been adapted in which time series prediction using LSTM turns out to be a better player. The method was successful in predicting the TCI Index with a level of precision. The chapter first covers the in-depth conclusion drawn from the study furthering suggesting some direction for future work.

6.2 CONCLUSION

The dissertation starts with an introduction to AI techniques involved in the prediction and forecasting techniques. The initial part of the dissertation discussed the problem outline in the current system methodology to achieve a desired outcome in addition to the study purpose. Based on the motivation described dissertation then summarized the various research papers, review papers used to study various prediction techniques deployed to predict the traffic congestion in various different scenario and further it discussed the techniques used to estimate road level vehicular emissions.

Additionally, it has clearly indicated that switching to a Deep Learning algorithm will improve prediction in a univariate dataset and enable implementation in a real-time environment. The explanation of the methods, technologies, and tools utilised to generate the suggested work is included in the dissertation's subsequent section. Based on the technique outlined above that was addressed in the suggested work implementation section and how it ended up being overcoming the flaws that have been stated in the beginning portion of the dissertation, the next chapter will detail how it overcame those weaknesses.

In the end, described a deep discussion on the results obtained. This dissertation proposes a TCI Index prediction model which could be used to predict traffic congestion covering the whole road network of New Delhi. The dataset was further used to create a vehicular CO emission inventory for the city. The method used was

successful in predicting the trend with a level of precision. The suggested LSTM model was shown to be appropriate for predicting the TCI Index for the city. The LSTM RNN deep learning strategy was used above as this algorithm is known to produce best result for time series prediction dealing with univariate dataset and as this was a novel work so this model was preferred to be used.

Further, TCI index was successfully used to map and prepare a high definition vehicular CO emission inventory for New Delhi over hourly flux of time using TCI Index eliminating the need for static monitoring devices, which is a completely new approach being used and had not been used for the city of New Delhi before. But these results are also indicating that the research methodology taken up has not been to perfectly predict the TCI index but has provided a high level of accuracy and as this was the first attempt to do the same, so it leaves an open ground for many further work in the area for improvement.

6.3 FUTURE SCOPE

The scope of the study revolves around the prediction of TCI Index and mapping vehicular emissions using the same for the city of New Delhi. Likewise this study could also be simulated for any other city for which the dataset of TCI is available. Further the scope of the model for prediction could be increased by deploying further advance techniques of prediction which are able to increase the accuracy and are able to more accurately identify the instantaneous changes in the traffic congestion.

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Researcher: Sawar Gupta

Supervisor: Dr. Vimlesh Kumar Ray

Department: Computer Science Engineering

School: School of Information and Communication Technology

Email ID (Researcher): sawar.gupta123@gmail.com

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This section reflects the basic introduction of AI techniques involved in the mapping and prediction over a large dataset. Later covers problem statement, objective of the study, and organization of complete study.

1.1 OVERVIEW

The use of vehicles has increased mobility for human activities, but it has also brought about a number of major problems, including air pollution, excessive fossil fuel use, and traffic congestion, all of which contribute to climate change. Vehicle emissions, which account for a significant portion of urban emissions like CO and NOX and others which significantly contribute to specific PM2.5 concentrations, which have significantly worsened air pollution issues for global megacities.

Also, traffic monitoring in the urban scenario has long been a major topic among academics and industry professionals, with the super-fast expansion of the metropolitan road network and the explosion of automobiles in recent decades, has led to more traffic congestion and hence more vehicular emissions.

Innumerable detectors and sensors have been mounted on fixed sites with short detection

ranges in traditional traffic monitoring systems to assist record diverse road conditions and road level traffic emissions across the network. Such systems have a lot of restrictions when it comes to range and efficacy. [1-4] However, the use of Data Science and Artificial

intelligence can solve a lot of these issues. Residents' daily lives may be made more pleasant and safe of hazardous pollution by utilizing technological innovation to assist the new experience.

Artificial intelligence can handle significant concerns faced by an increasingly urban population, such as traffic management, healthcare, energy problems, and a variety of other issues and this could also be implemented in real time. So it has the potential to enhance the lives of inhabitants and companies in a smart city.

So the matter of discussion arises what AI is and which components of AI could be used for

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